

Morphodynamic_Atlas_Tutorial

December 4, 2024

```
[1]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from pathlib import Path
from scipy import io
```

```
[2]: pd.set_option("display.notebook_repr_html", True)
```

1 Tutorial for querying the Drosophila Morphodynamic Atlas using python

The Drosophila morphodynamic atlas is a collection of 479 in-toto lightsheet-microscopy recordings of the Drosophila embryo at the blastoderm stage (stages 6-9). The atlas comprises 18 different genotypes.

The atlas data, including a description of the files and this tutorial, can be found on [Dryad](#), while the methodology and use of the atlas is the subject of the publication [Morphodynamic Atlas for Drosophila Development \(Mitchell et al, 2022\)](#).

Please see the `README.md` file on Dryad for details on the dataset.

This tutorial explains how to query the atlas for specific datasets and load the results into Python for inspection and analysis. You need the following python modules: `pandas`, `numpy`, `matplotlib`, and `scipy`. You further need the atlas database `Morphodynamic_Atlas.csv`, as well as the data you would like to load. The complete atlas is several 100GB large, so you can download just parts of it, e.g. for specific genotypes. All files can be found on the Dryad repository.

The code for querying the atlas uses the `pandas` (for database processing) and `pathlib` (for finding files on your hard drive) libraries. Both libraries are well-documented and popular and Google should be able to answer your usage questions.

We start by loading the database as a `pandas.DataFrame`. You need to place `Morphodynamic_Atlas.csv` in the same folder as this jupyter notebook. `pandas` is a powerful library for relational (“spreadsheet-like”) data in python and will allow us to select, group, and analyze the datasets in the atlas.

```
[3]: atlas_database = pd.read_csv('Morphodynamic_Atlas.csv')
atlas_database
```

```

[3]:
Embryo_ID \
0 ID of embryo (time of recording), in YYYYMMDDH..
1 202011021800
2 202011031830
3 202011071345
4 202011301820
.. ..
786 201908221210
787 201908221228
788 201908221236
789 201908221242
790 201908221248

Genotype \
0 Genotype. For organization purposes, recording..
1 67-15_1to3copies_UAS-Even-Skipped
2 67-15_1to3copies_UAS-Even-Skipped
3 67-15_1to3copies_UAS-Even-Skipped
4 67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-18W-HA
.. ..
786 toll [RM9]
787 toll [RM9]
788 toll [RM9]
789 toll [RM9]
790 toll [RM9]

Fluorophore \
0 Fluorescently tagged protein. For live recordi...
1 Sqh-GFP
2 Sqh-GFP
3 Sqh-GFP
4 Sqh-GFP
.. ..
786 Toll_8
787 Toll_8
788 Toll_8
789 Toll_8
790 Toll_8

Is_Live \
0 Live or fixed recording
1 True
2 True
3 True
4 True
.. ..
786 False

```

787	False
788	False
789	False
790	False

	Has_PIV \
0	Whether PIV (tissue flow fields) are available...
1	False
2	False
3	False
4	False
..	...
786	False
787	False
788	False
789	False
790	False

	Has_PIVLab \
0	Whether high-resolution PIV data (created by P...
1	False
2	False
3	False
4	False
..	...
786	False
787	False
788	False
789	False
790	False

	Timing_PIV \
0	Timing based on PIV. Indicates frame of movie ...
1	NaN
2	NaN
3	NaN
4	NaN
..	...
786	NaN
787	NaN
788	NaN
789	NaN
790	NaN

	Timing_Runt \
0	Timing based on Runt stripe 7 deformation. Ind...
1	NaN

2	NaN
3	NaN
4	NaN
..	...
786	NaN
787	NaN
788	NaN
789	NaN
790	NaN

Timing_Warped \

0	Timing based on Runt 7 stripe deformation, aft...
1	NaN
2	NaN
3	NaN
4	NaN
..	...
786	NaN
787	NaN
788	NaN
789	NaN
790	NaN

Timing_PMG_VF \

0	Timing based ventral or cephalic furrow for al...
1	NaN
2	NaN
3	NaN
4	NaN
..	...
786	NaN
787	NaN
788	NaN
789	NaN
790	NaN

Filename \

0	name of .tif file with image data. Note: some ...
1	202011021800_cylinder2_max_rot_scaled_view1.tif
2	202011031830_cylinder2_max_rot_scaled_view1.tif
3	202011071345_cylinder2_max_rot_scaled_view1.tif
4	202011301820_max_l14-23.tif
..	...
786	MAX_Cyl1_2_1_c000001_rot_scaled_view1.tif
787	MAX_Cyl1_2_1_c000001_rot_scaled_view1.tif
788	MAX_Cyl1_2_1_c000001_rot_scaled_view1.tif
789	MAX_Cyl1_2_1_c000001_rot_scaled_view1.tif

```
790          MAX_Cyl1_2_1_c000001_rot_scaled_view1.tif
```

	Time_Resolution_Seconds	Notes
0	Time resolution in seconds	Any additional notes about the dataset
1	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
2	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
3	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
4	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
..
786	NaN	NaN
787	NaN	NaN
788	NaN	NaN
789	NaN	NaN
790	NaN	NaN

```
[791 rows x 13 columns]
```

As you can see, each row corresponds to one recording. The first row explains the meaning of each column:

```
[118]: atlas_database.loc[0, "Embryo_ID"] # look at row 0, column "Embryo_ID" to see_
      ↪ what it this row means
```

```
[118]: 'ID of embryo (time of recording), in YYYYMMDDHHMM format'
```

1.1 Multichannel recordings

Note that for fixed datasets, a multi-channel image (e.g. for Fushi-Tarazu *and* Runt) will be listed as two recordings, with the same Embryo_ID.

```
[119]: # let's remove the first row to get the data only

atlas_database_data = atlas_database.iloc[1:].reset_index(drop=True)
```

2 Examples

We now show some examples of querying the atlas and loading some of the resulting data.

```
[120]: # let's list all available genotypes

atlas_database_data["Genotype"].unique()
```

```
[120]: array(['67-15_1to3copies_UAS-Even-Skipped',
          '67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-18W-HA',
          '67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped',
          '67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Runt',
          '67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Tollo-HA',
```

```
'67-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped', '67-singlecopy_UAS-Runt',
'Halo_Hetero_even-skipped[r13]_Hetero',
'Halo_Hetero_snail[IIG05]_Hetero',
'Halo_Hetero_twist[ey53]_Hetero', 'Halo_snail[IIG05]',
'Halo_twist[ey53]', 'TrafficJam-Gal4_UAS-Fat2RNAi',
'UAS-Even-Skipped', 'WT', 'WT_17_Degrees', 'bicoid[E1]_nanos[BN]',
'bicoid[E1]_nanos[BN]_tsl[4]', 'concertina-t48',
'even-skipped[r13]', 'spaetzle[A]', 'sqh[Ax3]', 'toll[RM9]'],
dtype=object)
```

```
[121]: # ... or tagged proteins
atlas_database_data["Fluorophore"].unique()
```

```
[121]: array(['Sqh-GFP', 'Bazooka-GFP', 'CAAX-mCherry', 'Runt', 'Bazooka',
'ECad-GFP', 'Even_Skipped', 'Even_Skipped-YFP', 'Fushi_Tarazu',
'H2a-mCherry_Klarsicht', 'Hairy', 'Moesin-GFP', 'Neurotactin',
'Paired', 'Shotgun-GFP', 'Sloppy_Paired', 'Sqh-mCherry', 'Tartan',
'Toll_6', 'Toll_8', 'endogenous_ECad-GFP', 'histone-RFP',
'ubiquitous-Rock-GFP', 'utr-mCherry', 'Histone-2B-RFP', 'ECad',
'CAAX-mCherry_Sqh-GFP'], dtype=object)
```

```
[122]: # let's find all fixed WT datasets which have been stained for Runt

filtered_data = atlas_database_data[(atlas_database_data['Genotype'] == 'WT')
& (atlas_database_data['Is_Live'] ==_
↳'False')
& (atlas_database_data['Fluorophore'] ==_
↳'Runt')]
```

```
[123]: filtered_data
```

```
[123]:      Embryo_ID Genotype Fluorophore Is_Live Has_PIV Has_PIVLab Timing_PIV \
215  201904121131      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
216  201904121153      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
217  201904121159      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
218  201904121410      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
219  201904121419      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
..      ...      ...      ...      ...      ...      ...
341  202010231850      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
342  202010231910      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
343  202101252010      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
344  202101252030      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN
345  202101252035      WT      Runt    False    False      False      NaN

      Timing_Runt Timing_Warped Timing_PMG_VF \
215      20.6      NaN      NaN
216      34.81      NaN      NaN
```

217	28.061	NaN	NaN
218	35.486	NaN	NaN
219	39.054	NaN	NaN
..
341	NaN	NaN	NaN
342	NaN	NaN	NaN
343	NaN	NaN	NaN
344	NaN	NaN	NaN
345	NaN	NaN	NaN

	Filename	Time_Resolution_Seconds	\
215	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
216	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
217	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
218	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
219	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
..
341	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
342	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
343	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
344	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN
345	MAX_Cyl1_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif		NaN

	Notes
215	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
216	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
217	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
218	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
219	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
..	...
341	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
342	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
343	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
344	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...
345	note: for analysis of runt, consider using the...

[125 rows x 13 columns]

2.1 A note on timing data

Depending on the data available for the recording, different timing information is available, based on the shape of Runt stripes (for fixed WT data), the tissue flow field (for live data), or the morphogenetic events of ventral furrow and cephalic furrow formation (for time alignment across different genotypes).

Note that the timing information is a single time stamp, corresponding to the timing of the first frame of the movie. For the fast-marching based “warped” time alignment (which assigns a different morphological time stamp to each frame), please use the full MATLAB based morpho-dynamic atlas

code base, available here: <https://github.com/npmitchell/dynamicAtlas>.

```
[124]: # assemble a pseudo-time line from fixed images of the pair-rule gene
↳Fushi-Tarazu

fushi_data = atlas_database_data[(atlas_database_data['Genotype'] == 'WT')
& (atlas_database_data['Is_Live'] == 'False')
& (atlas_database_data['Fluorophore'] ==
↳'Fushi_Tarazu')]

# subselect columns ID, timing, and file name, then sort by time (making sure
↳the computer knows the timestamps are numbers)

fushi_data = fushi_data[['Embryo_ID', 'Timing_Runt', 'Genotype', 'Fluorophore',
↳'Filename']]
fushi_data['Timing_Runt'] = pd.to_numeric(fushi_data['Timing_Runt'],
↳errors='coerce')
fushi_data = fushi_data.sort_values(by='Timing_Runt', ascending=True)

fushi_data
```

```
[124]:
```

	Embryo_ID	Timing_Runt	Genotype	Fluorophore	\
120	201905091624	1.0000	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
117	201905091543	2.5269	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
115	201905091402	6.4909	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
111	201905071651	6.6360	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
122	201905091640	16.1040	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
118	201905091557	17.1710	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
127	201905101422	20.8520	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
129	201905101440	22.1000	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
125	201905091719	22.8860	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
119	201905091604	24.9940	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
124	201905091714	27.9600	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
112	201905071659	31.8950	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
116	201905091409	32.0700	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
121	201905091633	33.3190	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
113	201905071718	34.6970	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
123	201905091648	34.9790	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
128	201905101432	36.3300	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
126	201905091724	38.8090	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	
114	201905091349	47.3730	WT	Fushi_Tarazu	

	Filename
120	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
117	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
115	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
111	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif

```

122 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
118 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
127 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
129 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
125 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
119 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
124 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
112 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
116 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
121 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
113 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
123 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
128 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
126 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
114 MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif

```

3 Loading image data

Let's load some of these `.tif` files. To do this, you first need to download the data from the [Dryad repository](#). There are stored there as compressed archive files (like `.zip`'s), one for each genotype - except for WT, which is broken up further into multiple archive files because of its large size.

Let's download the `WT_Fushi_Tarazu.tar.lz4` archive. On a unix-like system you can unpack it in the terminal via

```
~$ lz4 -d folder_name.tar.lz4 -c | tar xvf -
```

After unpacking the `WT_Fushi_Tarazu` folder, please restructure the directory structure as follows: 1. Create a `WT` directory 2. Move `WT_Fushi_Tarazu` in the `WT` directory 3. Rename `WT_Fushi_Tarazu` to `Fushi_Tarazu` This “undoes” the breaking-up of the WT genotype folder into multiple archives and will make it easier to load the files. You can of course automate this step if you want to.

Next, we will set the folder (“path”) where all the data is located. `Path.cwd()` will set it to the same folder that this jupyter notebook is located. You can also specify another folder, e.g. `Path(r"C:\Users\user\morphodynamic_atlas_data")`.

```
[65]: base_path = Path.cwd()
```

```
[66]: # let's print all the sub-directories in the base path to make sure we are in
      ↪ the right place.
      [f for f in base_path.iterdir() if f.is_dir()]
```

```
[66]: [PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-15_1to3copies_UAS-Even-Skipped'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT_17_Degrees'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
```

```

Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-18W-HA'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Runt'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/Halo_Hetero_even-skipped[r13]_Hetero'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/Halo_Hetero_snail[IIG05]_Hetero'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/Halo_Hetero_twist[ey53]_Hetero'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT_27_Degrees'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/bicoid[E1]_nanos[BN]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/toll[RM9]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/Halo_snail[IIG05]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_UAS-Runt'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/sqh[Ax3]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/UAS-
Even-Skipped'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/TrafficJam-Gal4_UAS-Fat2RNAi'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/Halo_twist[ey53]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/.ipynb_checkpoints'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/[INTERNAL] PIVlab_results'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/spaetzle[A]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Tollo-HA'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/even-
skipped[r13]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/[INTERNAL] timing'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/bicoid[E1]_nanos[BN]_tsl[4]'),
  PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of

```

```
Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/concertina-t48')]
```

```
[104]: # now, let's load the Fushi-Tarazu data. to do so, we iterate over the rows in
        ↪our filtered dataset
        # we the load the data and add it to our table

        fushi_data['Image'] = object # initialize the new row

        for index, row in fushi_data.iterrows():
            file_path = base_path.joinpath(row["Genotype"], row["Fluorophore"],
            ↪row["Embryo_ID"], row["Filename"])
            image = plt.imread(file_path)
            fushi_data.at[index, "Image"] = image
```

```
[113]: # let's look at the image data for a specific embryo

        selected_image = fushi_data[fushi_data["Embryo_ID"] == '201905091624']["Image"].
        ↪values[0]

        plt.imshow(selected_image)
```

```
[113]: <matplotlib.image.AxesImage at 0x7feca3339ed0>
```


4 Processing

You can now process the image(s) in whatever way you want: smooth them, compute gradients, correlate images across samples or genotypes, ...

We will leave this up to you.

5 Loading PIV data

For a subset of live recordings, we provide PIV data (tissue flow fields - please see the manuscript for a detailed explanation). There are two sets of PIV data whose presence is indicated by the `Has_PIV` and `Has_PIVLab` columns. They were computed with slightly different methods and saved in slightly different formats. `Has_PIV`-data is saved in a `PIV/` subfolder, with one file per timepoint and was computed using a custom script optimized for speed. `Has_PIVLab`-data was computed with the MATLAB add-on [PIV Lab](#), optimized for precision, and is saved as a single file per dataset. In both cases, the files are located in the same folder as all other data on the recording.

Since the PIV was created by MATLAB, they are in the `.mat` format. We can however read this format in Python without issue. Let's look at one example.

```
[125]: # list all recordings where PIVlab data is available
atlas_database_data[atlas_database_data['Has_PIVLab'] == 'True']
```

```
[125]:
```

	Embryo_ID	Genotype	Fluorophore	\
4	202011271230	67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped	Sqh-GFP	
5	202011271400	67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped	Sqh-GFP	
6	202011271520	67-singlecopy_15-singlecopy_UAS-Even-Skipped	Sqh-GFP	
25	202007011145	Halo_Hetero_twist[ey53]_Hetero	Sqh-GFP	
26	202007081130	Halo_Hetero_twist[ey53]_Hetero	Sqh-GFP	
27	202007091200	Halo_Hetero_twist[ey53]_Hetero	Sqh-GFP	
47	202101201045	Halo_snail[IIG05]	Sqh-GFP	
54	202101221425	Halo_snail[IIG05]	Sqh-GFP	
60	202101281300	Halo_snail[IIG05]	Sqh-GFP	
61	202007171100	Halo_twist[ey53]	Sqh-GFP	
62	202007171400	Halo_twist[ey53]	Sqh-GFP	
64	202007301030	Halo_twist[ey53]	Sqh-GFP	
374	202001101100	WT	Sqh-mCherry	
376	202001120940	WT	Sqh-mCherry	
379	202001252040	WT	Sqh-mCherry	
464	202201311320	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
465	202201311600	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
466	202202011630	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
467	202201311320	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
468	202201311600	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
469	202202011630	WT_17_Degrees	Sqh-mCherry	
530	202001151953	even-skipped[r13]	Sqh-GFP	

532	202001171624	even-skipped[r13]	Sqh-GFP
533	202001181115	even-skipped[r13]	Sqh-GFP
554	201712191340	spaetzle[A]	Sqh-GFP
556	201712201630	spaetzle[A]	Sqh-GFP
557	201712201930	spaetzle[A]	Sqh-GFP
755	202101111920	toll [RM9]	Sqh-GFP
756	202101121810	toll [RM9]	Sqh-GFP
757	202101191940	toll [RM9]	Sqh-GFP

	Is_Live	Has_PIV	Has_PIVLab	Timing_PIV	Timing_Runt	Timing_Warped	\
4	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
5	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
6	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
25	True	False	True	22	NaN	NaN	
26	True	False	True	17	NaN	NaN	
27	True	False	True	23	NaN	NaN	
47	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
54	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
60	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
61	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
62	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
64	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
374	True	True	True	18	NaN	NaN	
376	True	True	True	8	NaN	NaN	
379	True	False	True	14	NaN	NaN	
464	True	False	True	36	NaN	NaN	
465	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
466	True	False	True	18	NaN	NaN	
467	True	False	True	36	NaN	NaN	
468	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
469	True	False	True	18	NaN	NaN	
530	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
532	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
533	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
554	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
556	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
557	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
755	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
756	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	
757	True	False	True	NaN	NaN	NaN	

	Timing_PMG_VF	Filename	\
4	7	cylinder1_max.tif	
5	15	cylinder1_max.tif	
6	1	cylinder1_max.tif	
25	0	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif	
26	5	orig_MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif	

27	-1	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
47	8	202101201045_SnailMinus_l8-13.tif
54	8	202101221425_SnailMinus_l5-10.tif
60	4	202101281300_SnailMinus_l7-12.tif
61	-1	202007171100_twistMinus_l6-11.tif
62	-10	202007171400_twistMinus_l6-11.tif
64	-2	202007301030_twistMinus_l6-11.tif
374	4	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
376	12	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
379	8	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
464	-8	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c0_rot_scaled_view1.tif
465	0	cylinder1_max_6to14.tif
466	4	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c0_rot_scaled_view1.tif
467	-8	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c0_rot_scaled_view1.tif
468	0	cylinder1_max_6to14.tif
469	4	MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c0_rot_scaled_view1.tif
530	11	NaN
532	-1	NaN
533	11	NaN
554	-9	cylinder1_max.tif
556	-11	cylinder1_max.tif
557	-3	cylinder1_max.tif
755	-6	cylinder1_c1_max.tif
756	-8	cylinder1_max.tif
757	-8	cylinder1_c1_max.tif

	Time_Resolution_Seconds	Notes
4	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
5	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
6	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
25	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
26	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
27	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
47	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n\nImaged by ...
54	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n\nImaged by ...
60	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n\nImaged by ...
61	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
62	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
64	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: CyoSqhGFP\n
374	NaN	NaN
376	NaN	NaN
379	NaN	NaN
464	NaN	NaN
465	NaN	NaN
466	NaN	NaN
467	NaN	NaN
468	NaN	NaN

469	NaN		NaN
530	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: cyoSqhGFP\n	
532	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: cyoSqhGFP\n	
533	NaN	fluorofore chromosome: cyoSqhGFP\n	
554	NaN		NaN
556	NaN		NaN
557	NaN		NaN
755	NaN		NaN
756	NaN		NaN
757	NaN		NaN

```
[154]: # let's pick one of the WT recordings
```

```
selected_embryo = atlas_database_data.iloc[376]
selected_embryo
```

```
[154]: Embryo_ID                202001120940
Genotype                       WT
Fluorophore                     Sqh-mCherry
Is_Live                         True
Has_PIV                         True
Has_PIVLab                      True
Timing_PIV                      8
Timing_Runt                     NaN
Timing_Warped                   NaN
Timing_PMG_VF                   12
Filename                       MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif
Time_Resolution_Seconds         NaN
Notes                           NaN
Name: 376, dtype: object
```

```
[155]: # let's list all the files we have for this recording
```

```
selected_embryo_path = base_path.joinpath(selected_embryo["Genotype"],
↳selected_embryo["Fluorophore"], selected_embryo["Embryo_ID"])

sorted(selected_embryo_path.iterdir())
```

```
[155]: [PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/Sqh-
mCherry/202001120940/202102181445_time.txt'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/Sqh-
mCherry/202001120940/MAX_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/Sqh-
mCherry/202001120940/MEAN_Cyl11_2_000000_c1_rot_scaled_view1.tif'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/Sqh-
mCherry/202001120940/PIV'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/Sqh-
mCherry/202001120940/PIV_filtered'),
```

```

PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/WT_202001120940_PIVlab.mat'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/cephallicFurrowOnset.txt'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/tOV.txt'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/timematch_Runt_cephallicFurrowOnset.txt'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/timematch_linearOffset_curlSign.txt'),
PosixPath('/mnt/data/flydrive_clone/clean copy of Atlas_Data/Atlas_Data/WT/SqmCherry/202001120940/timematch_linearOffset_vmagAlign.txt')]

```

The file we need is [...]_PIVlab.mat. Let's load it. The result of loading a .mat file is a dictionary comprising the x and y components of the PIV field, and the grid on which they are defined. Please see the [PIV lab website](#) for detailed documentation.

```

[160]: mat_file_path = [f for f in selected_embryo_path.iterdir() if str(f).endswith(".
↳mat")] [0]
mat_file = io.loadmat(mat_file_path)

mat_file.keys()

```

```

[160]: dict_keys(['__header__', '__version__', '__globals__', 'uu_lst', 'vv_lst',
'u_filt_lst', 'v_filt_lst', 'xx', 'yy'])

```

```

[161]: # u_filt_lst and v_filt_lst contain the arrays of x and y components of the
↳(filtered) PIV field across the timepoints of the movie
# (here, 39).

mat_file["uu_lst"].shape

```

```

[161]: (89, 151, 107)

```

```

[162]: # let us visualize the flow field at one time oint using a stream plot

timepoint = 30

plt.streamplot(mat_file["xx"], mat_file["yy"], mat_file["u_filt_lst"][30],
↳mat_file["v_filt_lst"][30])
plt.axis("equal")

```

```

[162]: (21.0, 1717.0, 21.0, 2421.0)

```

